

A TWO-WAREHOUSE INVENTORY SYSTEM FOR NON- INSTANTANEOUS DETERIORATING PRODUCTS WITH INFLATION

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KEYWORDS

ABSTRACT

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This paper presents an EOQ model for non- decaying products and inflation has becoming a common thing regarding medicinal products during pandemic COVID-19. An inventory system is established with two-warehouse where the function of demand is based on selling price. Shortages are allowed with the condition of partially backlogged. The rate of backlogging is exponentially decreasing as the time of waiting increases. Further, the system has been established with condition: the products of owned warehouse are consumed after this consume the rented warehouse products. An EOQ model is established for non- decaying products and inflation has becoming a common thing regarding medicinal products during pandemic COVID-19. A numerical example is taken to demonstrate this system and sensitivity analysis has been explored by captivating one parameter at a time keeping the other parameters unchanged.

INTRODUCTION

Various firms buy more than needed because of concession that they receive during a bulk purchase thus avoiding the ordering cost etc. To store the extra purchase forms of often rent a warehouse. In the rented warehouse the per unit holding and deterioration costs are greater than the owned one. The items are first stocked up in OW and when the surplus stock should be stored in RW. To lessen the total

inventory cost it is needed to finish the stock of rented warehouse first and then consume the one stored in OW. The large capacity of on the warehouse also declines the total system cost. Thus, studying the system of two warehouse is very important while formulating an inventory model

Inflation refers to the rise in the prices and is often related to time. It occurs by a decline in the purchasing power which varies with time. Many scholars often pay no attention to the conception of inflation when the frame the ideal of study because there is complicatedness in reducing the cash flows that occur during the inventory arrangement. At major times profitability does not consider inflation.

Demand is a vital factor in any trade process. The retailing procedure any item makes changes in the action of the customer and the demand remains constant which is not real. The demand varies with the selling cost. Therefore, it becomes important to manage the selling cost in order to control the demand.

1. Literature Review

In inventory two warehouse model was first developed by Hartely [1] in 1976 with the condition that rented warehouse has higher holding cost then owned warehouse. So, the product of rented warehouse is used firstly after this the product of owned warehouse are consumed. In this model, shortages not allowed. Pakkala and Acharya [2] addressed a two-warehouse structure with partial backlogging shortages for deteriorating items. Wee [10] formulated the inventory policy for two warehouse system demand is based on selling price. Yang [11] presented a two-warehouse system for declining products where shortages are allowed and function of demand is fixed. Singh et al. [3] offered a model with two warehouses under the impact of inflation for non-instantaneous deteriorating products. Shortages are partially backlogged. The capacity of owned warehouse is fixed where the capacity of rented warehouse is unlimited. Singh et al. [4] recommended an inventory model with two warehouse policies where demand is a function of instantaneous level of stock. Shortages are allowed with partially backlogging condition. They gave an offer of permissible delay in payment to the customers. Shaikh and Bhunia [5] developed inventory system for deteriorating products with shortages. The facilities of two separate storage are given in this policy with different preservation technology. The rate of demand is a combined function of time and selling price.

Kumar et al. [6] presented a two- warehouse inventory model for non-instantaneous decaying products with shortages. The effect of inflation and learning on the inventory policy is considered to established the model. Yadav et al. [12] introduced a two-warehouse inventory system where deterioration is considered as Weibull distribution with shortages. The demand function is ramp type. Shah and Naik [7] investigated the policy of inventory with price sensitive demand rate for non-instantaneous decaying products.

Sundararajan et al. [8] investigated the policy for Price determination of a non-immediate worsening items with shortage and inflation under delay in payment. Tayal et al. [9] formulated an inventory

structure to find the optimal ordering quantity of non-immediate worsening items with partly backlogging shortages.

Hence, we have done an effort to connect the factor defined appropriate in a single problem. Thus, a system for non-instantaneous items with demand of price and partial backlogging is used here.

3. Notations and Assumptions

Notations

1. α, β - demand variables
2. D - demand rate
3. T - cycle time
4. t_2 - time at which stock level begin to be zero in OW
5. t_1 - time at which stock level begin to be zero in RW
6. $I_r(t), I_o(t)$ - The level of stock at time t in RW & OW
7. γ, δ - deterioration parameter in OW and RW respectively, $0 < \gamma, \delta < 1$.
8. Z - storage capacity of owned warehouse
9. I - ordering quantity
10. W - storage capacity of rented warehouse
11. C_p - purchasing cost per unit
12. $\theta(\mu)$ - rate of backlogging
13. μ - backlogging parameter
14. C_{ho} - holding cost in OW
15. C_{hw} - holding cost in RW
16. C_o - ordering cost
17. C_π - shortage cost
18. C_l - lost sale cost
19. C_d - deterioration cost
20. R - inflation rate
21. $T.P.$ - total profit
22. C_s - selling cost

23. I_1 - At the beginning of cycle, the level of stock

Assumptions

1. Demand is related to selling cost and shown as $D(P) = \alpha C_s^{-\beta}$.
2. Lead time is supposed to be zero.
3. Owned warehouse has a fixed capacity and Rented warehouse has unlimited capacity.
4. Shortages of stock are permitted and partly backlogged. The backlogging rate is a function of waiting time up to the next arrival and $(T - t)$ is waiting time during $t_1 \leq t \leq T$ & $\theta(\mu) = e^{-\mu(T-t)}$.
5. The rate of inflation is constant.
6. For the system of inventory, time horizon is infinite.
7. Deterioration takes place after the life time of items. After fixed time $t = t_1$ deterioration starts in Rented warehouse.

4. Mathematical Model Formulation

(Figure 1: Graphical representation of Two-warehouse inventory system)

The inventory functioning time of the system is drawn in figure1. At $t = 0$, I be the inventory level. After receiving the products from the backorder, I_1 products enter in the system. From which W

are kept in RW and rest $Z = (I_l - W)$ are kept in OW. Inventory level of RW during time $[0, t_1]$ reduces due to market demand and deterioration. At $t = t_1$, it turns out to be zero. After this between (t_1, t_2) , stock level of OW reduces due to market demand and process of deterioration. At $t = t_2$, it turns out to be zero. During the time interval $[t_1, T]$ occurring shortages and shortage of products is partly backlogged or lost and $I = I_l + D(T - t)$.

The level of stock in the rented-warehouse is describing by the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dI_r(t)}{dt} + \delta I_r(t) = -\alpha C_s^{-\beta}, 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{1}$$

The solution of equation (1) subject to the boundary condition $I_r(0) = W$

is as:

$$I_r(t) = \left(W + \frac{\alpha C_s^{-\beta}}{\delta} \right) e^{-\delta t} - \frac{\alpha C_s^{-\beta}}{\delta}, 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{2}$$

Now at $t = t_1, I_r(t) = 0$

$$\text{we get } t_1 = \frac{1}{\delta} \log \left(1 + \frac{\delta W}{\alpha C_s^{-\beta}} \right) \tag{3}$$

During time $[0, t_1]$, stock level of OW is Z and there is no deterioration during time $[0, t_1]$. So, the level of OW is Z . The following differential equation shows the level of stock in the owned-warehouse:

$$\frac{dI_o(t)}{dt} + \gamma I_o(t) = -\alpha C_s^{-\beta}, t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \tag{4}$$

The solution of equation (4) subject to the boundary condition $t = t_1, I_o(t) = Z$

is as:

$$I_o(t) = \left(Z + \frac{\alpha C_s^{-\beta}}{\gamma} \right) e^{\gamma(t_1-t)} - \frac{\alpha C_s^{-\beta}}{\gamma}, t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \tag{5}$$

At $t = t_2, I_o(t) = 0$

$$t_2 = t_1 + \frac{1}{\gamma} \log \left(Z + \frac{\gamma S}{\alpha C_s^{-\beta}} \right) \tag{6}$$

After t_2 , shortages start then,

$$\frac{dS(t)}{dt} = -\alpha C_s^{-\beta} \left(e^{-\lambda(T-t)} \right), \quad t_2 \leq t \leq T \tag{7}$$

The solution of equation (5.33) subject to the boundary condition $t = t_2, s(t) = 0$

is as:

$$S(t) = \frac{\alpha C_s^{-\beta}}{\lambda} \left(e^{-\lambda(T-t_2)} - e^{-\lambda(T-t)} \right) \tag{8}$$

The different cost for the inventory system is as follows:

$$\text{Ordering Cost} = C_o \tag{9}$$

$$\text{Shortage Cost} = \int_{t_2}^T -C_\pi e^{-Rt} (S(t)) dt \tag{10}$$

$$= \frac{C_\pi \alpha C_s^{-\beta}}{\lambda} \left[\frac{e^{-\lambda T}}{(\lambda - R)} \left\{ e^{(\lambda - R)T} - e^{(\lambda - R)t_2} \right\} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{e^{-\lambda(T-t_1)}}{R} \left\{ e^{-Rt_2} - e^{-RT} \right\} \right] \tag{11}$$

$$\text{Lost Sale Cost} = e^{-RT} \int_{t_2}^T \alpha C_s^{-\beta} C_l (1 - e^{-\gamma(T-t)}) dt \tag{12}$$

$$= C_l \alpha C_s^{-\beta} e^{-RT} \left[(T - t_2) - \frac{1}{\lambda} \left\{ 1 - e^{-\lambda(T-t_2)} \right\} \right] \tag{13}$$

$$\text{Purchasing Cost} = C_P I \tag{14}$$

$$= C_P \{ I_1 + D(T - t_2) \} \tag{15}$$

$$\text{Holding Cost in Rented Warehouse} = C_{hr} \left[\int_0^{t_1} I_r(t) e^{-Rt} dt \right] \tag{16}$$

$$= \frac{C_{hr}}{R(R + \delta)} \left\{ RW + D(e^{-Rt_1} - 1) \right\} \tag{17}$$

$$\text{Holding Cost in Owned Warehouse} = C_{ho} \left[\int_0^{t_1} I_o(t) e^{-Rt} dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} I_o(t) e^{-Rt} dt \right] \tag{18}$$

$$= \frac{ZC_{ho}}{R(R + \gamma)} \left\{ R + Z(1 - e^{-Rt_1}) + \frac{D}{Z} (e^{-Rt_2} - e^{-Rt_1}) \right\} \tag{19}$$

$$\text{Deterioration Cost} = C_d \left[\int_0^{t_1} \delta I_r(t) e^{-Rt} dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \gamma I_o(t) e^{-Rt} dt \right] \tag{20}$$

$$= C_d \left[\frac{\delta}{R(R + \delta)} \left\{ RW + D(e^{-Rt_1} - 1) \right\} + \frac{\gamma}{R(R + \gamma)} \left\{ D(e^{-Rt_2} - e^{-Rt_1}) + RZe^{-Rt_1} \right\} \right] \tag{21}$$

$$\text{Sales Revenue} = C_s \left[\int_0^{t_2} De^{-Rt} dt + e^{-RT} \int_{t_2}^T De^{-\lambda(T-t)} dt \right] \tag{22}$$

$$= C_s D \left\{ \frac{1}{R} (1 - e^{-Rt_2}) + \frac{e^{-RT}}{\lambda} (1 - e^{-\lambda(T-t_2)}) \right\} \tag{23}$$

$$\text{Total Profit} = \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{Sales Revenue} - \text{Ordering Cost} \\ - \text{Shortage Cost} - \text{Lost Sale Cost} \\ - \text{Purchasing Cost} - \text{Deterioration Cost} \\ - \text{Holding Cost in Rented Warehouse} \\ - \text{Holding Cost in Owned Warehouse} \end{array} \right) \tag{24}$$

$$T.P. = \left[\begin{aligned} & C_s D \left\{ \frac{1}{R} (1 - e^{-Rt_2}) + \frac{e^{-RT}}{\lambda} (1 - e^{-\lambda(T-t_2)}) \right\} \\ & - C_p \{ I_l + D(T - t_2) \} - C_o \\ & - \frac{C_\pi D}{\lambda} \left[\begin{aligned} & \frac{e^{-\lambda T}}{(\lambda - R)} \{ e^{(\lambda-R)T} - e^{(\lambda-R)t_2} \} \\ & - \frac{e^{-\lambda(T-t_1)}}{R} \{ e^{-Rt_2} - e^{-RT} \} \end{aligned} \right] \\ & - C_l D e^{-RT} \left[(T - t_2) - \frac{1}{\lambda} \{ 1 - e^{-\lambda(T-t_2)} \} \right] \\ & - \frac{C_{hr}}{R(R + \delta)} \{ RW + D(e^{-Rt_1} - 1) \} \\ & - C_d \left[\begin{aligned} & \frac{\delta}{R(R + \delta)} \{ RW + D(e^{-Rt_1} - 1) \} \\ & + \frac{\gamma}{R(R + \gamma)} \{ D(e^{-Rt_2} - e^{-Rt_1}) + RZe^{-Rt_1} \} \end{aligned} \right] \\ & - \frac{ZC_{ho}}{R(R + \gamma)} \left\{ R + Z(1 - e^{-Rt_1}) + \frac{D}{Z} (e^{-Rt_2} - e^{-Rt_1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \right] \tag{25}$$

5. Procedure for Solution

The motive of this chapter is to maximize the total profit of system. The necessary condition is

$$\frac{\delta T.P.}{\delta I_l} = 0, \frac{\delta T.P.}{\delta C_s} = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$\text{the sufficient conditions are } \frac{\partial^2 T.P.}{\partial I_l^2} \leq 0, \frac{\partial^2 T.P.}{\partial C_s^2} \leq 0 \tag{26}$$

6. Numerical Example

Let $\alpha = 100000$, $\beta = 2$, $C_o = 140$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\delta = 0.06$, $Z = 100$, $C_p = 10$,

$C_{ho} = 1$, $C_{hw} = 1$, $\mu = 0.06$, $R = 0.06$, $T = 1$, $C_\pi = 2$ & $C_l = 4$.

Then, $t_1 = 0.432$, $t_2 = 0.871$, $C_s = 22.145$, $Q_f = 188.24$ and $Q = 211.56$.

7. Sensitivity Analysis

Here, we study the effect of inflation on the inventory system.

(i) When deterioration rate $\gamma = \delta = 0.06$ is given. Then impact of inflation on two-warehouse system.

Table: 1 (Impact of Inflation on Inventory System when $\gamma = \delta$)

R	C_s	I_l	I	$T.P.$
0.02	21.61	197.57	219.21	2133.66
0.04	21.82	194.15	214.92	2088.94
0.06	22.04	190.77	210.77	2045.22

(Figure 2: Graphical representation of Impact of Inflation)

(ii) When deterioration rate $\gamma = 0.1$ and $\delta = 0.06$ is given. Then impact of inflation on two-warehouse system.

Table: 2 (Impact of Inflation on Inventory System when $\gamma > \delta$)

R	C_s	I_l	I	$T.P.$
0.02	21.72	196.01	220.08	2107.24
0.04	21.90	193.82	216.75	2062.50
0.06	22.02	187.19	212.54	2017.81

(Figure 3: Graphical representation of Impact of Inflation)

(iii) When deterioration rate $\gamma = 0.06$ and $\delta = 0.1$ is given. Then impact of inflation on two-warehouse system.

Table: 3 (Impact of Inflation on Inventory System when $\gamma < \delta$)

R	C_s	I_l	I	$T.P.$
0.02	20.76	202.11	232.14	2128.16
0.04	21.08	200.32	219.84	2102.34
0.06	21.37	198.21	217.80	2041.23

(Figure 4: Graphical representation of Impact of Inflation)

8. Conclusion

The main aim of this inventory system is to establish two-warehouse model for non-instantaneous deteriorating products which jointly improve the selling price and initial stock by boosting total profit. The effect of inflation is also taken. Shortages are allowed with partial backlogged condition. If the deterioration rate of owned warehouse and rented warehouse is equal and inflation rate is rising then total profit is reducing.

The future extension for this two-warehouse system is stock dependent demand, lead time and finite replenishment rate etc.

9. Reference

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